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K-10 CURRICULUM: SOLUTION TO DECONGESTION

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The K–10 curriculum will shortly be released by the Department of Education (DepED), although it will not take the place of the K–12 curriculum. So, what exactly is this K to 10 all about? DepED has conducted a thorough study of the Kindergarten through Grade 10 (K–10) curriculum, which will possibly be implemented in the 2024–2025 academic year according to Undersecretary and Spokesperson Poa. The revised curriculum attempts to temporarily "decongest" the school system to improve the overall standard of the country's fundamental education by giving more time to important topics like mathematics, instruction in values, science, reading, and English.

In a similar vein, DepED intends to use online or hybrid education or learning to simplify schools more quickly and effectively without sacrificing educational quality. Additionally, the DepEd made the draft curriculum available for scrutiny by the public in April and May, and it generated a lot of feedback from professionals, academics, and members of the general public.

A task group to investigate the SHS program and current policies was established by DepEd last May this year, in order to ensure uniformity, responsiveness, and adaptability to the circumstances of the learners and stakeholders. Bringas claims that the task force would also look at how the program is addressing market demands while considering worries regarding the employability of SHS graduates. The task team was told to deliver its findings and recommendations the following year.

The K–10 curriculum will include the following suggestions, according to Assistant Secretary Bringas.

Reduction of learning areas

Sibika, Kultura, Kasaysayan, at Kagalingang Pangkatawan (SIKaP), a new subject that incorporates Araling Panlipunan and the music, arts, physical education, and health, will be offered to learners in grades 1 to 3. Likewise, the separate mother tongue topic will also be dropped, but the primary grades will still use it as the primary language of instruction. The number of learning areas in the foundation years or from Grades 1 to 3 will be reduced. Additionally, DepEd has been urged by a number of organizations to bring back the separate Philippine history course in junior high school, but the group has not stated whether the recommendation will be included in the final version of the redesigned curriculum. DepEd is also recommending a separate reading and language subject for Grade 1 that will also be taught in the student's mother tongue.

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Opening of classes

The start of the academic year 2023–2024 will still be in August. Concerning the review of the K–12 curriculum, according to Poa, is still in progress. DepEd established a public task group in May to examine how the senior high school curriculum was being implemented.

Promotion of Peace Education

The integration of peace competences into the new K–10 curriculum will place special emphasis on the encouragement of nonviolent activities and the development of students' conflict-resolution skills. The promise of K–12 education is that students would be employable, but we must confess that this is not the case now. Officials from DepEd are examining strategies to match market demands, improve employability, and increase our students' desire to find employment.

The K–12 curriculum will be updated, according to Vice President and Education Secretary Sara Duterte, in order to generate graduates who are better qualified, prepared for the workforce, active, and responsible.

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